

Video Documented Upscaled Synthesis of Salts of the Parent Carbaborate Ion $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$, its Undecafluorinated Form $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ and Useful Starting Materials for its Introduction

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In memory of Josef Michl, a true pioneer in the field of carbaborate chemistry and many other areas.

In this work, we present our improved protocols for the single batch syntheses of approximately 32 g of $[\text{NHMe}_3][\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$ and 10 g of $\text{Na}[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ as well as salt metathesis reactions, granting access to useful starting materials to introduce the $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ anion. This includes the trityl cation $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}]^+$ and the bis-1,2-difluorobenzene-silver(I)-complex $[\text{Ag}(\text{odfb})_2]^+$, as well as

some applications of the shown compounds. The described methodology allows the synthesis of large amounts of both the $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$ and the $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ anion and therefore making them accessible for further reactions. To facilitate the reproducibility, we present video tutorials of the synthetic steps towards $\text{Na}[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$.

Introduction

Carbaborates, including their alkylated and halogenated derivatives, are a class of anions with a wide variety of potential applications. Their main advantage is their low negative charge, which is delocalized over the entire cluster (for $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ see Figure 1) and makes them suitable weakly coordinating anions (WCAs).^[1–3] WCAs are a class of anions, which feature a large diameter as well as delocalized charges and therefore reduced coordination abilities of the anion.^[4–6] Thus, WCAs find widespread applications in fields such as catalysis, electrochemistry, materials and battery science as well as in the isolation of novel and reactive cationic species.^[2–11] However, every group of WCAs has a characteristic set of strengths and weaknesses. Carbaborates and their halogenated derivatives usually show a high thermal as well as (electro-) chemical stability against oxidation^[75,76] and strong Lewis acids.^[1–3] This makes the anion interesting not only for applications with silylium ions or silylium ion catalysis,^[12–15] but also for catalysis that involves

Figure 1. Projection of the calculated electrostatic potential of the $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ anion onto its isodensity surface (0.025 electrons Bohr^{-3}). Regions with a high negative charge are marked in red, while regions with a positive charge are shown in blue. Calculated on the RIJ-BP-D3BJ/def2-SVP level of theory.

other Lewis acidic cationic compounds, for example in olefin polymerization,^[16,17] or the use in electrochemistry.^[4,7,18,19]

Many of the frequently used WCAs are heavily fluorinated. Currently, the EU plans to ban compounds that feature a variety of structural motives with fluorinated carbon atoms, under which a considerable number of established WCAs like $[\text{Al}(\text{OC}(\text{CF}_3)_3)_4]^-$, $[\text{B}(3,5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CF}_3)_2)_4]^-$, TfO^- , Tf_2N^- , or Tf_3C^- (with $\text{Tf} = \text{F}_3\text{C-SO}_2-$) would fall. These would therefore no longer be applicable for future commercial applications.^[20] The carbaborate $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$ and its derivatives present an obvious alternative as a high performance WCA, as they usually feature no C-F bonds. Yet, despite several improvements, the bottleneck for all

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different boron compounds $[\text{BH}_4]^-$, $[\text{B}_3\text{H}_8]^-$ and $[\text{B}_9\text{H}_{14}]^-$ in ^{11}B -NMR spectra taken during the reaction (see Figure 2), which is in accordance with the findings of Below *et al.*^[35] Their concentration decreases over time, in favor of the formation of $[\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]^-$. Therefore, we assume that $[\text{B}_3\text{H}_8]^-$ and $[\text{B}_9\text{H}_{14}]^-$ are intermediates of the synthesis. In 1970, Dewkett *et al.* used similar reaction conditions to directly synthesize $[\text{B}_3\text{H}_8]^-$ and reported the formation of volatile B_2H_6 (see Equation 3f in Scheme 1), which they quantitatively detected by injecting the exhaust fumes into an aqueous silver nitrate solution.^[43] This also enlightens the first steps in the reaction (see Scheme 1).

In our initial reactions, we suffered from the formation of high amounts of side products, as well as low yields of approximately 30%. We deduced, that both observations must result from the formation of B_2H_6 , which removes boron hydrides from the mixture and thus reduces the yield. Schulz *et al.* reported, that they observed the formation of pyrophoric gasses and violent explosions during the reaction, forcing them

to rely on specialized personal protective equipment, as well as safety shields. Furthermore, they also reported lowered yields of 15–32%.^[32] This report corroborated our assumptions, however, we never observed such violent behavior. Thus, we assumed that we could suppress the formation of B_2H_6 in favor of the productive reaction path by keeping the concentration of $[\text{BH}_4]^-$ in the solution high (see Equation 3b in contrast to 3f) to facilitate its easy subsequent reaction with $\text{BH}_3\cdot\text{OR}_2$ ($\text{OR}_2 = \text{diglyme}, \text{Et}_2\text{O}$) to $[\text{B}_2\text{H}_7]^-$. This can be accomplished in several ways: Due to the poor solubility of $\text{Na}[\text{BH}_4]$ in diglyme, its concentration can be stabilized by the use of larger amounts of solvent or simply upscaling the reaction. In our studies, larger batch reactions (150 g of $\text{Na}[\text{BH}_4]$ in approximately 0.8 L of solvent) usually performed better than smaller ones. Furthermore, the addition rate of the reagent, be it $\text{BF}_3\cdot\text{OEt}_2$ or bromopentane, has an influence on the concentration of $[\text{BH}_4]^-$, because a fast addition rate converts all the available $[\text{BH}_4]^-$ into $\text{BH}_3\cdot\text{OR}_2$, leaving none for the subsequent reaction. Thus, in our hands an addition rate as slow as possible worked best. For the upscaled reactions, we chose a rate of 1 drop every 1 or 2 seconds, allowing an addition rate of 100–120 mL per day and stretching the addition of the reagent over 6 d in our largest batch. The third important factor is the provision of sufficient stirring. For scales as the ones reported here, an overhead stirrer is essential (we would not recommend to use magnetic stir bars for scales larger than 15 g of $\text{Na}[\text{BH}_4]$), due to the massive amounts of solid $\text{Na}[\text{BF}_4]$ or NaBr forming during the reaction (see Figure 3, right), which give the mixture a slush-like texture when stirred. Note, that per gram of product, typically 9 g NaBr or 8 g $\text{Na}[\text{BF}_4]$ are formed! Thus, the use of overhead stirrers is necessary to transport the reagent to all areas of the reaction vessel. Combining all three approaches, we were able to meet and even exceed literature yields, while never observing dangerous reaction behavior, both during the reaction as well as the workup.

Reaction Procedure: The reaction can be stopped and restarted at will. However, the temperature should be well equilibrated before the addition is restarted. Before shutting down the reaction, the mixture should be stirred at 105 °C for at least 15 min and then cooled down. When ventilating the setup, inert gas should not be injected through the entire setup, but instead from the exhaust side (see Figure 3, above the reflux condenser), to prevent the B_2H_6 , which probably is present in the headspace of the reaction flask, from being flushed out of the setup. Once the addition is finished, we recommend to analyze the reaction mixture by NMR, for the presence of significant amounts of side products. These usually

Figure 2. ^{11}B -NMR (top: 128 MHz, bottom: 96 MHz, diglyme, rt) of the reaction mixture of $\text{Na}[\text{BH}_4]$ and $\text{BF}_3\cdot\text{OEt}_2$ at half the addition (top) and after the full addition of $\text{BF}_3\cdot\text{OEt}_2$ (bottom). All intermediates described in the text can be seen. Note that the NMR signals of $\text{BF}_3\cdot\text{OEt}_2$ and $[\text{BF}_4]^-$ fall onto one due to exchange and shift slightly, depending on the concentration of its components.

Scheme 1. Proposed reaction steps in the formation of $[\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]^-$, based on the findings of Dewkett *et al.*^[43] as well as our own observations. The unproductive pathway, leading to the formation of diborane, is shown in red.

Figure 3. Left: Schematic setup for the synthesis of $[B_{11}H_{14}]^-$, both using $BF_3 \cdot OEt_2$ and Pent-Br as reagent. Right: Filling height with settled, solid $Na[BF_4]$ at a late stage of the reaction. The photo is taken of a 60 g $Na[BH_4]$ scale reaction, the shown flask is a 2 L round bottom flask. For reactions in the same scale, but using bromopentane as reagent, the amount of solid formed is comparable.

can be further converted into product by the addition of more reagent. Small amounts of side products are acceptable and could not be avoided entirely from our experience.

The reaction setup shown in Figure 3 is related to the one of Dunks and Ordonez, who first reported the protocols in 1978 and 1981.^[29–30] It consists of a reaction flask, equipped with a dropping funnel and an overhead stirrer. Furthermore, gaseous diethyl ether or *n*-pentane, as well as dihydrogen gas form during the reaction and have to be discharged from the setup. For that, the exhaust fumes are injected into an ice cooled round bottom flask, equipped with a reflux condenser to condense the ether or *n*-pentane. The remaining gasses are led through an oil-bubbler into a trap with acetone, to neutralize volatile boron hydrides, which might still form during the reaction. On several occasions we were able to detect boric esters in the acetone, as a product of the reaction between B_2H_6 and acetone, and furthermore got single crystals of the boroxine $(B(iPrO)O)_3$ (for single crystal X-ray diffraction structure, see SI).

Workup: For the workup, at first the mixture is vacuum filtered on air. At this point, the use of bromopentane shows its advantage, since the formed NaBr has a crystalline form, which makes it notably easier to filter off and rinse. By contrast, $Na[BF_4]$ mixed with the diglyme solvent adopts a gel like texture. It is therefore much harder to filter off and requires more time and solvent to be rinsed colorless.

As the next step, the solvent has to be removed. Due to the thermal instability of $Na[B_{11}H_{14}]$ ^[27] the diglyme has to be distilled from the mixture under vacuum. We screened for different conditions (see Table 1) and therefore recommend the

Table 1. Screening for optimum distillation conditions to remove diglyme from the reaction mixture. For this, 20 mL reaction mixture portions were worked up using different conditions. The respective times and yields are given relative to the longest time and the highest yield obtained.

Conditions	Rel. Distillation Time	Rel. Yield
$8 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mbar, 50 °C heating	75 %	83 %
16 mbar, 75 °C heating	100 %	100 %
16 mbar, 95 °C heating	42 %	93 %
16 mbar, 105 °C heating	38 %	49 %

removal at 16–20 mbar at an oil bath temperature of 85 °C for optimum yield and time expenditure, since we observed product decomposition at 95 °C. For approximately 1 L of diglyme this takes around 1.5 d. Since either residual ether or *n*-pentane will evaporate from the mixture during the distillation, the use of a -78°C cooling trap between the setup and the pump is highly encouraged.

The addition of water to remove the diglyme as an azeotropic mixture was tested as well, but in our experience, it took twice as long, both using distillation setups as well as rotary evaporators.

The remaining $Na[B_{11}H_{14}]$ was reported to react pyrophoric.^[31] Although we never observed this behavior ourselves, we would therefore recommend not to dry it entirely, but to leave residual amounts of diglyme in it and to limit the time it is exposed to air in solid state.

Afterwards, the solid yellow material is dissolved in a minimum of water. The addition of water can be dangerous if large amounts of side products are present, therefore, the first drops of water should be added very slowly. In the worst case, the mixture heats up rapidly and forms a foam, that ascends in the flask. If the synthesis was performed properly, almost no reaction occurs upon the addition of water. Usually, we heat the final aqueous mixture to around 40 °C to obtain a clear solution. In our experience, undissolved solid is also product. The product is then precipitated by the addition of an aqueous solution of $[NHMe_3]Cl$. The precipitated product is filtered off and washed with water to remove unreacted $[NHMe_3]Cl$. Then the solid is dissolved in acetone, best when it is still wet with water, and briefly heated to reflux. Dissolving the product in acetone is not merely a step of recrystallization but more a step of chemical purification, as we believe it neutralizes smaller boron clusters. We observed this reaction, which presents itself by a slow gas formation, to be more controlled in the presence of water. In our first attempt we experienced a runaway reaction, which started spontaneously upon heating, until the solvent was evaporated completely and the residue solidified entirely, probably also due to the presence of large amounts of smaller clusters in the mixture. Thus, we now add additional water to the mixture to facilitate it at lower temperatures. As $[B_{11}H_{14}]^-$ was reported to reduce acetone under acidic conditions,^[35] we try to limit the time it is dissolved in it. After heating the mixture, additional water is added and the organic solvent is removed under rotary evaporation, until the product

some minutes under reflux. Using this method, we were able to exclude the formation of the fluorinated cation. It is technically a combination of methods used both by Kütt and Leito, as well Michl, although none of them discussed the formation of the difluoromethyltrimethylammonium cation in their respective publication.^[27–28]

To the refluxing mixture, $\text{Me}_3\text{Si-CF}_3$ is added dropwise over approximately 3 h. The mixture is heated for several days to provide the full conversion. For the workup strategy, Kütt and Leito's method has proven to be the most yielding for us. It involves the neutralization of the remaining NaH with water and the removal of the organic solvent, before an aqueous solution of $[\text{NHMe}_3]\text{Cl}$ was added to precipitate the product. The heterogeneous mixture is extracted by ethyl acetate and the combined organic layers are washed, freed from solvent and dried under vacuum. Simply isolating the precipitated material gave product with poor quality. Using this strategy, the product was obtained in batches up to 32 g with 72% yield in one reaction. The product can be further purified via crystallization from ethyl acetate by layering with *n*-pentane if needed (for single crystal X-ray diffraction structure, see SI).

Another issue we observed in upscaled $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$ reactions was the formation of small amounts of monofluorinated $[\text{2-CB}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{F}]^-$ under the reaction conditions (see Figure 4). The reaction pathway to monohalogenated clusters was first reported in the literature for the syntheses of $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$ via dichloro- and dibromocarbenes, and has been extensively described by Michl *et al.* in theoretical studies.^[26–27] However, neither Kütt and Leito nor Michl reported the formation of said compound.^[27–28] Currently we typically observe an impurity of

approximately 4–10%, using both literature known methods involving $\text{Me}_3\text{Si-CF}_3$. Unfortunately, we were so far unable to separate $[\text{2-CB}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{F}]^-$ from the mixture. We expect the fluorinated anion to occupy sites of the $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$ statistically in the crystal structures and have therefore not been able to identify it by single crystal or powder XRD. Since our goal was to synthesize the undecafluorinated anion $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ anyway, we did not further investigate how to avoid the formation or how to separate $[\text{2-CB}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{F}]^-$ in our studies.

Shortcuts Attempted: Furthermore, we tried to synthesize $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$ directly from the untreated reaction mixture of the $[\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]^-$ synthesis in a one-pot reaction approach (see Scheme 2). The key idea was to bypass the time-consuming workup of the $[\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]^-$ (see Equation 8c in Scheme 2), as well as to avoid the introduction of trimethylammonium, just to remove it again in the next step. Furthermore, it is rather convenient, that the reaction mixture of the $[\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]^-$ synthesis in diglyme is already free of moisture and air. In addition, Michl *et al.* showed in their studies that diglyme is a suitable solvent for the $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$ synthesis.^[27]

In fact, by using this protocol, we were able to obtain $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$. However, it was always contaminated with unreacted $[\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]^-$ and we were suffering from a generally low yield, poor product quality, unwanted side reactions and required high excesses of reagents. The key problem of the method is that $[\text{BH}_4]^-$ is formed during the deprotonation of $[\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]^-$, probably from side products of the previous reaction step. We then observed the formation $\text{Me}_3\text{Si-CHF}_2$, which is the literature-known product of the reaction of $[\text{BH}_4]^-$ and $\text{Me}_3\text{Si-CF}_3$,^[48,49] that no longer participates in the reaction. The best conditions we were able to achieve after an extensive survey were by using 5.1 eq. of KH as base and 6.5 eq. of $\text{Me}_3\text{Si-CF}_3$, yielding approximately 36% product with a 4:1 ratio of $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$ and $[\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]^-$. Therefore, we stopped our investigations in this seemingly elegant direction.

Conversion to $\text{M}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$ ($\text{M}=\text{Na}$, Cs): To synthesize $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$, $[\text{NHMe}_3][\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$ was reacted with sodium hydroxide (see Equation 9) and heated to reflux, while compressed air was injected into the mixture to remove the formed trimethylamine. Instead, vacuum could be applied, but in our experience the use of compressed air reduces the uncomfortable odor of the trimethylamine, when the exhaust gasses are

Figure 4. ^{19}F , ^{11}B -COSY NMR spectrum (377 MHz, MeCN-d_3 , rt) of $[\text{2-CB}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{F}]^-$. The crosspeak of the fluorine and the boron resonances of the B–F vertex is shown. Center: ESI(–)-mass spectrum of the $[\text{2-CB}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{F}]^-$ as well as its theoretical isotope pattern.

Scheme 2. Schematic idea for the shortcut-approach: In the regular synthesis, the $\text{Na}[\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]$ is worked up to $[\text{NHMe}_3][\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]$, which is then deprotonated back to $\text{Na}[\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]$ before the cluster itself gets deprotonated to $[\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{13}]^{2-}$. This detour could be avoided in theory by using the reaction mixture as starting material for the second synthetic step. (Reagents: a) $\text{BF}_3\cdot\text{OEt}_2$ or bromopentane in diglyme, b) NaH; $\text{Me}_3\text{Si-CF}_3$ in THF or diglyme).

led directly into the fume hoods back. The resulting mixture was filtered, to remove unreacted starting material or impurities, before it was neutralized and extracted by ethyl acetate. The combined organic layers were freed from solvent under reduced pressure and the remaining oil was intensively dried under high vacuum at 180 °C for several days. An easy indicator for the dryness of the Na[CB₁₁H₁₂] is, when the product is not sintering anymore while being heated, but remains powdery. Explanatory video footage for this reaction is available in the Supporting Information.

The Cs⁺ salt was synthesized in a similar way (see Equation 10), however, the extraction was performed with diethyl ether, and thus, a pH neutralization beforehand was not necessary. Therefore, less care can be taken to remove residual trimethylamine and the mixture was not refluxed, but only compressed air was injected into the mixture during the reaction. Furthermore, the product is easier to dry and usually 150 °C was a sufficient temperature. Crystals of Cs[CB₁₁H₁₂] suitable for X-ray crystallography were grown via vapor diffusion of *n*-pentane into a solution in diethyl ether (see SI).

Synthesis of [CHB₁₁F₁₁]⁻

In Organic Media: The carbaborate [CB₁₁H₁₂]⁻ undergoes fluorination in a reaction with elemental fluorine F₂ or F₂/N₂ mixtures.^[36–39] In our initial attempts, we tried to establish this fluorination by injecting fluorine mixtures (30% in nitrogen) into organic solutions of [NHMe₃][CB₁₁H₁₂]. There, we focused our attempts on acetonitrile as solvent (see Equation 12), as it was used in the perfluorination of its all-boron congener [B₁₂H₁₂]²⁻ by Strauss *et al.* in 2009^[50] and later by us as well (see Equation 11).^[51] The original reaction protocol uses KF as HF-scavenger, that allowed the deployment of glassware as reaction vessel. We chose to use the [NHMe₃]⁺-salt, as it did not require a preliminary salt metathesis reaction and previous works in our groups showed that the fluorination of alkylammonium cations is unfavored in the α -position.^[52]

However, we solely received incomplete fluorinated product (see Figure 5). Even with as many as 66 eq. of fluorine gas, the targeted [CHB₁₁F₁₁]⁻ anion was never observed as the main product. Changing the reaction conditions, dryness of solvent as Strauss *et al.* did in their protocol,^[50] or using the Cs⁺-salt as starting material did not change the results.

In anhydrous HF (aHF): After this setback we tried to reproduce the literature known routes in aHF,^[36–39] featuring sealed reactors with a 30% fluorine mixture atmosphere and were granted immediate success. The reaction of Cs[CB₁₁H₁₂], as well as [NHMe₃][CB₁₁H₁₂] or Na[CB₁₁H₁₂], with 11 eq. of fluorine gas gave [CHB₁₁F₁₁]⁻ as the only fluorinated cluster (see Equation 13).

However, as we are limited to the use of 30% fluorine gas mixtures in nitrogen, we calculated, that the synthesis of

Figure 5. ESI(–)-mass spectra of the products of the reaction of [NHMe₃][CB₁₁H₁₂] (except g, see below) with F₂ (30% in N₂) in commercial acetonitrile, with KF at 0 °C. Conditions: a) 5.5 eq. of F₂, b) 11 eq. of F₂, c) 22 eq. of F₂, d) 33 eq. of F₂, e) 66 eq. of F₂, f) two subsequent reactions: 22 eq. of F₂ in commercial MeCN, isolation of product and 66 eq. of F₂ in dried MeCN and with dried KF (see Strauss protocol),^[50] g) Cs[CB₁₁H₁₂] with 22 eq. of F₂.

$[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ in a decagram scale would take months of reaction time in the vessels at our disposal and reconsidered the route. Instead, we designed the fluorination in aHF featuring an open flow setup (see Figure 6, center), similar to our reactions in acetonitrile. The setup was built from PFA and glass parts. The reaction vessel is a commercially available column component, produced by SAVILLEX,^[53] equipped with a cap with two inlets, that allows to inject gas, as well as to remove its exhaust (see Figure 6, left). According to the manufacturer, these vessels are resistant to pressures of up to 5 bar^[53] and are therefore perfect for the handling of medium scaled reactions in aHF. All exhaust gasses were injected into another column component filled with soda-lime to neutralize both hydrogen fluoride and fluorine, and afterwards in a glass trap, filled with an aqueous solution of KI and Na_2CO_3 . The trap was originally used to neutralize the fluorine gas in our reactions in acetonitrile and serves now both as a backup trap and flow control indicator.

The reactor itself was charged with starting material in a glovebox and aHF (small scales: approximately 50 mL, large scales up to 300 mL) was condensed into it. None of the starting material salts we used actually dissolved completely in aHF. The mixture was stirred overnight in the sealed vessel, as Strauss *et al.* reported that the fluorination of the 12-position of the cluster proceeds already with aHF under the formation of hydrogen.^[37] Then, the reactor was connected to the remaining setup, cooled to -40°C to prevent the aHF from evaporating

and the fluorine gas mixture was injected by mass flow controllers (9.5 mL/min F_2 and 23.0 mL/min N_2 for 30% F_2 in N_2). After the completed reaction, the headspace of the system was flushed with nitrogen, before the reactor was sealed off and taken from the setup. Then, the solvent was removed by evaporating it under reduced pressure over soda-lime and the residue was dried *in vacuo*.

Fluorination Conditions and Influence of Starting Salts: In our initial reactions featuring this setup, we experienced serious problems with clogging gas inlets, since they were designed to actually reach into the solution. This was solved by shortening them, to end about 1 cm over the solutions level. Again, we tested the three starting materials $[\text{NHMe}_3][\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$, as well as the Cs^+ and Na^+ salt, all with utilizing 22 eq. of fluorine gas. We experienced that the $[\text{NHMe}_3]^+$ salt underwent poor fluorination, as it was swimming on top of the solvent and tended to stick on the vessel walls, making it inaccessible for the reaction. In the reactions with the Cs^+ and Na^+ salts, we obtained $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ as the main product. However, the Cs^+ salt was contaminated with notable amounts of the decafluorinated $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_2\text{F}_{10}]^-$. The Cs^+ salt was also more prone to clog the gas inlet. We postulate that these findings are caused by the increased solubility of $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$ in aHF, as it is a mismatched ion-pair in terms of Pearson's HSAB concept. Since the synthesis of $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$ is also notably cheaper, we focused on the fluorination of $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$. Note that we were never able to

Figure 6. Left: Picture of the PFA-column vessel (small version), manufactured by SAVILLEX. Center: Schematic reaction setup for the fluorination of $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$ used in this work. Components shown in blue are made of PFA, FEP or Teflon. At the red markings the setup can be disassembled to remove the reactor. Note, that the gas inlet tube ends approximately 1 cm above the liquid. Right: Picture of the reaction vessel during the synthesis.

reach full conversion to $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ in subsequent fluorinations of $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_2\text{F}_{10}]^-$ containing products in sealed systems and with reasonable amounts of fluorine gas. Thus, the content of $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_2\text{F}_{10}]^-$ in the product should be kept at a low level.

Using 0.6 g batches of $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$ as starting material, we repeatedly observed full fluorination to $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ with 22 eq. of F_2 . However, upon scaling the reactions to 0.5–1.5 g of starting material, we observed the formation of erratic amounts of $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_2\text{F}_{10}]^-$ in the product, even with different amounts of fluorine up to a very large excess.

The calculations of the gas-phase Gibbs free energy for the fluorination on the RIJCOSX-B3LYP-D3BJ/def2-TZVPP level of theory revealed, that the fluorinations on the boron vertices are notably exergonic, while the fluorination of the carbon vertex is less favored by approximately 200 kJ mol^{-1} , but still exergonic (see Equation 14 in Scheme 3). We furthermore calculated every possible combination of the last two observed fluorination steps, but were unable to find a combination which explained our struggle to achieve the full fluorination (see SI). Therefore, we conclude, that the incomplete fluorination must be caused by kinetic reasons.

To address this problem synthetically, we made several experiments with varying reaction conditions, which included the addition of more fluorine, temperature variations, application of UV-light, the use of additives and sonication (see Table 2).

Since the use of more fluorine gas did not prove to be successful (see Table 2, II), we considered conducting the reaction at higher temperatures to overcome kinetic barriers.

Therefore, we made two experiments, in which we either raised the temperature to $+5^\circ\text{C}$ during the addition (see Table 2, III), or applied static pressure of 30% F_2 gas at 35°C (see Table 2, IV). Both experiments did not solve the issue. For further activation, we irradiated the reaction mixture with UV light at -40°C during the addition of 3 eq. of F_2 (see Table 2, V), again with limited success.

Instead we considered, that the late fluorination might be hindered by protonated clusters, caused by Brønsted acidic decomposition products of the reaction like tetrafluoroboric acid, similar to the suggestions of Strauss *et al.* in his fluorinations of $[\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}]^{2-}$ in acetonitrile.^[50] We therefore tried to neutralize those by the addition of KF and therefore generate quasi-alkaline conditions in aHF. The addition of 10 w% KF resulted in a slight improvement (see Table 2, VI), the addition of 20 w% of KF in a deterioration of side product content (see Table 2, VII).

Finally, we reached the conclusion, that the incomplete reaction might be caused by solubility limitations. In that case, small particles of material would feature an undecafluorinated shell, with an insufficiently fluorinated core. To overcome this, we applied ultrasound to the mixture during fluorination. We used a submersible sonicator probe for this process, as in our experience typical sonicator baths tend to fail from short circuits, when filled with liquid at sub-ambient temperatures due to internal condensation. However, the low temperature was required to prevent the solvent from evaporating. Using this technique, we were able to almost entirely rule out the formation of the decafluorinated $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_2\text{F}_{10}]^-$ (see Table 2, VIII),

Scheme 3. Calculated Gibbs free energy of the average fluorination steps on the RIJCOSX-B3LYP-D3BJ/def2-TZVPP level of theory at 298 K.

Table 2. Summary of experiments to reach full undecafluorination on $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$ in the open fluorination system. All reactions used aHF and 30% F_2 in N_2 (9.5 mL/min F_2 and 23.0 mL/min N_2). Note that not all experiments were conducted with the same batch of starting material or the same fluorine gas tank. Furthermore, some of the product samples contained small amounts of $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{F}_{12}]^-$.

	Amount $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$	Conditions	$[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_2\text{F}_{10}]^- : [\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$
I	0.5 g	22 eq. F_2 at -40°C	1:6.0 (14.3%)
II	2.5 g	24 eq. F_2 at -40°C	1:3.4 (22.7%)
III	1.5 g	14 eq. F_2 at -40°C and 4 eq. F_2 at $-40 \rightarrow 5^\circ\text{C}$	1:3.8 (20.8%)
IV	0.5 g	22 eq. F_2 at -40°C and 0.67 eq. F_2 static at 35°C	1:7.0 (12.5%)
V	0.5 g	19 eq. F_2 at -40°C and 3 eq. F_2 at -40°C with UV light irradiation	1:6.8 (12.8%)
VI	1.5 g	22 eq. F_2 at -40°C , with 10 w% KF	1:7.0 (12.5%)
VII	0.8 g	22 eq. F_2 at -40°C , with 20 w% KF	1:3.3 (23.3%)
VIII	0.5 g	22 eq. F_2 at -40°C , with sonication	1:46.7 (2.1%)
IX	0.5 g	16 eq. F_2 , at -40°C , with sonication	1:11.4 (8.1%)

although we observed the minor formation of $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{F}_{12}]^-$ instead, with a ratio of approximately 33:1. This species was seldomly observed in previous experiments and was so far not reported in the literature as a side product of this reaction. We were able to identify it both in ^{19}F -NMR, as well as in mass spectrometry (see Figure 7). In the latter, we furthermore underwent mass spectrometry experiments with the addition of D_2O to rule out that the signal was caused by a hypothetical $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, which would show the same m/z and an almost identical isotope pattern.

In our efforts to synthesize pure $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$, we therefore reduced the amount of fluorine gas applied to the mixture to

Figure 7. ^{19}F - ^{13}C -HMBC-NMR (377 MHz, CD_3CN , rt, optimized for coupling constants of 250 Hz) of $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{F}_{12}]^-$ as a trace impurity in $\text{Na}[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$. The crosspeak clearly indicates the $^1J_{\text{FC}}$ coupling of the carbon bound fluorine atom with the ^{19}F resonance at $\delta = -245.8$ ppm, to the carbon vertex with a ^{13}C signal at $\delta = 60.8$ ppm. The coupling constant is $^1J_{\text{FC}} = 290$ Hz. Center: Signal of $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{F}_{12}]^-$ in the ESI(-)-mass spectrum of the product, as well as its theoretical isotope pattern.

Figure 8. ESI(-)-mass spectra of fluorination products of the upscaled reactions: a) 6.5 g of $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$ with 28 eq. of F_2 , b) 5 g of $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$ with 22 eq. of F_2 under sonication. The main signal set at 341 m/z represents the $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ anion.

16 eq. and received a mixture of $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_2\text{F}_{10}]^-$ and $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ again (see Table 2, IX).

Scale up: For small scale syntheses, we therefore concluded to recommend the use of 22 eq. of F_2 and ultrasonic enhancement for the given setup. Two examples of scale up experiments underline the importance for optimized reaction conditions in small scale applied to upscaled reactions. In a first reaction (see Figure 8a), we fluorinated 6.5 g of $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$ with 28 eq. of F_2 in aHF, which gave a highly broadened distribution of fluorination products, with $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ as the main product, but with the presence of lower fluorinated clusters down to $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_6\text{F}_6]^-$. This example clearly shows, how the problems of the reaction multiply during scale up, compared to the small-scale experiments. In a second experiment (see Figure 8b), of which we present video documentation in the Supporting Information, we used 5 g of $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$, 22 eq. of F_2 and the sonication device during the entire synthesis. In that case we received a mixture of approximated ratio $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_2\text{F}_{10}]^- : [\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^- : [\text{CB}_{11}\text{F}_{12}]^-$ of 5.3:33.3:1. We were therefore able to show the application of our synthetic method to scales of about 9.9 g of product (90%) which currently is the largest reported synthesis of $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ by amount to our knowledge.

Product Composition: Besides the side products described above, the crude fluorination product contains $[\text{BF}_4]^-$ salts ($[\text{BF}_4]^- : [\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ of 1:7.4), as well as a BF_3 adduct ($\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Do} : [\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ of 1:10.5). Both are generated by the decomposition of $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ under excessive fluorination and cannot be avoided in our experience. However, the product was of sufficient quality to continue with the salt metatheses without workup. Before doing this, it should be dried under high vacuum at 130°C for some hours. This was preferred over the typically performed isolation of $[\text{NHMe}_3][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$,^[37-39] which needs another synthetic step by deprotonating the $[\text{NHMe}_3]^+$ cation with the respective alkaline hydroxide in water and therefore excessive drying. However, by treating $[\text{NHMe}_3][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ with CsOH , followed by extraction with Et_2O , we were able to grow crystals of $\text{Cs}[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ by evaporation of the solvent (see Figure 9).

Structure of $\text{Cs}[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$: The structure of $\text{Cs}[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ allowed us to estimate the anions radius by the distance between the anions center and the most populated cation site of 580.01(13) pm. The Cs^+ cation on this site is coordinated by 11 fluorine atoms, therefore Shannons effective ionic radius reported for this cation is 185 pm,^[54] giving the $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ anion a radius of 395 pm. Alternatively, we determined the shortest distance between two cluster centers to be 688.80(0) pm, giving the anion a radius of 344.40 pm. The thermochemical ionic volume^[55-56] of the $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ anion can then be determined from the volume of unit cell, Z and the Goldschmidt volume of the Cs^+ cation^[56] to be 0.3083 nm^3 .

When only considering the most populated Cs^+ site, the structure of $\text{Cs}[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ resembles a distorted CsCl packing, however, the Cs^+ is displaced towards one square of anions. Described in other words, there is a system of planar anion monolayers along the b,c -plane, between which the cations are located, either more towards the one or the other layer. We

Figure 9. Molecular structure of Cs[CHB₁₁F₁₁] with the thermal ellipsoids at 50% probability. The structure features two different Cs sites, each disordered twice. For better visibility, only the most populated Cs site (58%) is shown. (*P*₂/*c*, *R*₁: 3.10%, *wR*₂: 8.39, *a* = 9.8123(4) Å, *b* = 9.7298(4) Å, *c* = 13.9267(6) Å, *α* = *γ* = 90°, *β* = 100.272(2)°).

therefore assume, that the material might be able to conduct Cs⁺ cations in at least one dimension. The layers themselves consist of anions, packed in a checkboard structure, as they form squares. The next layer is slightly shifted in the *b* direction, but not in *a*. Compared to the reported structures of Cs-[CHB₁₁Br₁₁],^[57–58] the [CHB₁₁F₁₁][−] anion is perfectly ordered, but the structure is solved in a space group of lower symmetry. The structure of Cs[CHB₁₁Br₁₁] features a layer like structure as well, however, the cations are located deeper inside the layers and the [CHB₁₁Br₁₁][−] anions are arranged in a 2D dense sphere packing.^[57]

Properties of [CHB₁₁F₁₁][−]

Redox Stability: The crude Na[CHB₁₁F₁₁], which was obtained from the fluorination as described above, was treated with the potent oxidation agent XeF₂, with which it reacted under violent combustion upon getting in contact under Ar (see Equation 15 in Scheme 4). With [O₂][SbF₆] it reacted under the same violent combustion, when grinding the solids in a mortar

Scheme 4. Summary of reactions between crude Na[CHB₁₁F₁₁] and a selection of oxidizers and reducing agents.

without a mediator solvent under nitrogen (see Equation 15). Both reactions resulted in insoluble decomposition product(s). It is unknown, if this reaction behavior is caused by the [CHB₁₁F₁₁][−] itself, or by impurities such as [CB₁₁H₂F₁₀][−].

Regarding reducing agents, we reacted the crude Na[CHB₁₁F₁₁] with an excess of sodium, Li[AlH₄] and Na[BH₄] at rt over one week in THF, as a selection of representative reducing agents. Please note that the crude Na[CHB₁₁F₁₁] also contained residues of Na[BF₄], which did react with the reagents as well. The reaction of crude Na[CHB₁₁F₁₁] with sodium in THF (see Equation 16) yielded the monohydrogenated [12-CB₁₁HF₁₀]^{2−} dianion as the main product, in which the hydrogen is located on the vertex opposite to the carbon. Strauss *et al.* found the same substitution in their studies under these conditions.^[36] We found another product with a similar ¹⁹F{¹¹B}-NMR-signal pattern as the main product. Judging from the signals in the ESI(−)-MS (see SI), we assume that the dianion reacted with residual oxygen and formed the alkoxide dianion Na₂[1,12-OCB₁₁HF₁₀]. When adding THF to a mixture of Na[CHB₁₁F₁₁] and Li[AlH₄] (see Equation 17), an immediate gas formation was observed, caused by the hydrogen generating deprotonation of the cluster to form the dianion [CB₁₁F₁₁]^{2−}, which was later identified by NMR. However, no further reaction with the cluster vertices was observed. The Na[BF₄] in the mixture was transformed into Na[BH₄]. In the third reaction of Na[CHB₁₁F₁₁] and Na[BH₄] in THF (see Equation 18), only unreacted starting material was found in the NMR analysis.

To rationalize the redox stability of the anion, we conducted CV experiments with [Bu₄N][CHB₁₁F₁₁] in acetonitrile to determine the size of the solvent window (see SI). In our first experiments, we determined a stability of the compound of about +2 to −1.75 V against Fc/Fc⁺, when used as the support electrolyte. However, this could be even larger, if the solvent was dried more thoroughly.

Water Stability: It was reported by Strauss *et al.* that [CHB₁₁F₁₁][−] reacts under partial hydrolysis in aqueous alkaline conditions.^[37] With respect to current political developments to ban fluorinated compounds due to their lack of biodegradability, we decided to test the stability of our obtained crude Na[CHB₁₁F₁₁] in deionized and natural water, the latter was obtained from a local pond close to our chemistry department.^[59] Each sample of Na[CHB₁₁F₁₁] was dissolved in the respective water and NMR experiments were conducted over six months. Both showed the decrease of signals of [CHB₁₁F₁₁][−] in the ¹⁹F{¹¹B}-NMR. [2-CHB₁₁F₁₀(OH)][−] was identified by ESI(−)-MS as the sole product in natural water and as the major product in deionized water. However, the first species to decompose was the [BF₄][−] ion, which was present as a side product from the previous step. Thus, we determined the waters pH after six months with standard indicator paper to be 1, which made the results even more surprising to us, as Strauss *et al.* reported the anion to be stable in aqueous acids.^[37] In a buffered pH, the hydrolysis of Na[CHB₁₁F₁₁] will probably progress further in this timescale. These results indicate that [CHB₁₁F₁₁][−] might be a suitable replacement candidate for commercial applications in catalysis or as electrolytes, in case that the more commonly used C–F-bond containing WCAs like

$[\text{B}(\text{Ar}^{\text{F}})_4]^-$ (with $\text{Ar}^{\text{F}} = 3,5\text{-(CF}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3$), $[\text{TfO}]^-$ (with $\text{Tf} = \text{SO}_2\text{-CF}_3$) or $[\text{Al}(\text{OR}^{\text{F}})_4]^-$ (with $\text{R}^{\text{F}} = \text{C}(\text{CF}_3)_3$) would be banned. Nevertheless, this is only a first indication for biodegradability and needs a more specific research. On the other hand, this probably indicates the limits of long-term applications of $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ salts in aqueous systems.

Salt Metatheses of $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ to useful Starting Materials

$[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$: The crude fluorination product can be stirred with trityl bromide in CH_2Cl_2 for one week to give $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ (see Equation 19 in Figure 10). The mixture was filtered to remove residual sodium bromide and washed with *n*-pentane under sonication to remove unreacted trityl bromide. However, since this purification method fails to remove all unwanted trityl compounds, we recrystallized the compound from a CH_2Cl_2 -solution, layered by *n*-pentane. Using this method, we were able to crystallize $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ as orange needles, suitable for single crystal XRD (see Figure 10). The bulk purity could be shown by powder XRD as well (see SI). The same reactions can be performed with trityl chloride, however, we obtained lower yields (63 %) and a lower product quality.

Although the compound is known to the literature,^[36–38] its structure has not been published so far. However, the structure of the chlorinated derivative $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{Cl}_{11}]$ is known.^[60] The structure of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ (see Figure 10) was solved in the space group $Pca2_1$ and features no additional solvent molecules in the cell. Cation and anion form linear columns that are oriented along the *c*-direction. Therefore, the central carbon atom of the $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}]^+$ does not interact with fluorine atoms, instead the trityl groups are flatly packed on top of each other, while being staggered to the next unit. The phenyl rings are oriented in the other direction as the next unit, though. On average, they are tilted by 30.8° . The distance between the central carbon atoms is 417.71(13) pm, which rules out any interaction between them. The anion is entirely ordered and the shortest H–F distance between cation and anion is 245.47(14) pm. The structure differs highly from the structure of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{Cl}_{11}]$, as the $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}]^+$ cation is oriented towards the anion there and features distances between the anion and the central carbon, which are almost within the sum of the respective van der Waals radii.^[60]

Figure 10. Synthesis of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ from $\text{Na}[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ and trityl bromide. Molecular structure of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ with a thermal ellipsoid probability of 50 % ($Pca2_1$, R_1 : 3.29 %, wR_2 : 9.10 %, $a = 23.5884(6)$ Å, $b = 12.7242(3)$ Å, $c = 8.3349(5)$ Å, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$).

Application in Hydrosilylation: The obtained $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ was then used as an activator for a hydrosilylation reaction (see Equation 20) as a scope for one of its possible use cases. For that, 1-hexene and triethylsilane were mixed in a NMR tube and 2 mol % $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ was subsequently added. The NMR analysis showed the full conversion of both the triethylsilane and the 1-hexene to triethylhexylsilane, as well as scrambling products.

$[\text{Ag}(\text{oDFB})_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$: The salt metathesis to the Ag^+ salt was performed using AgF in liquid SO_2 (see Equation 21a in Figure 11). The suspension was stirred at rt over approximately one week in a double Schlenk tube. The mixture was filtered through a G4 frit and the solvent was evaporated. We were initially interested in the solvent-free Ag^+ salt, however, we suffered from water contaminations, either from our starting material or our solvent, so that the $[\text{Ag}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ prepared in this manner contained traces of water. Since we did not expect the silver salt to withstand a drying process at elevated temperatures, we decided to remove the water by recrystallization from 1,2-difluorobenzene (*o*DFB) and *n*-pentane, yielding the bis-arene complex $[\text{Ag}(\text{oDFB})_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ (see Equation 21b). The literature known $[\text{Ag}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6)][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ was of little interest to us, as the benzene both lowers the oxidative potential of the silver ion, as well as might act as a nucleophilic species in further applications. *o*DFB instead is a tolerable compound, as it can be used as a solvent for reactions involving quite Lewis acidic compounds.

Using single crystal XRD, we determined the structure of $[\text{Ag}(\text{oDFB})_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ (see Figure 11). The structure was solved in the space group $Pbca$ and shows an asymmetric unit of one cation and one anion. The silver is η^2 coordinated by two *o*DFB molecules in their 4 and 5 positions. The arenes are oriented in opposite directions. One *o*DFB molecule coordinates the ion with almost equal bond lengths of 244.5(2) and 245.8(2) pm, while the other coordinates unsymmetrical with bond lengths of 241.5(2) and 252.28(19) pm. Furthermore, the silver ion is

Figure 11. Synthesis of $[\text{Ag}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ and $[\text{Ag}(\text{oDFB})_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$. The molecular structure of $[\text{Ag}(\text{oDFB})_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ is shown with thermal ellipsoids of 50 % probability ($Pbca$, R_1 : 3.87 %, wR_2 : 9.57 %, $a = 11.5630(9)$ Å, $b = 17.0945(13)$ Å, $c = 22.0441(16)$ Å, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$).

coordinated by three fluorine atoms of different anions at contact lengths of 264.57(12), 277.30(12) and 309.73(12) pm. Moreover, it is very weakly coordinated by the two fluorine atoms of an *o*DFB unit in a neighboring cation with bond lengths of 283.53(13) and 368.67(16) pm, of which the latter is beyond the sum of the van der Waals radii of silver and fluorine (360 pm).^[61] Of the structurally characterized arene coordinated silver carborate salts^[62–67] $[\text{Ag}(\text{odfb})_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ is structurally most similar to the $[\text{Ag}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6)_2][\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{F}]$, reported by Soltnev and Strauss,^[63] or $[\text{Ag}(\textit{p}\text{-Me}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{Cl}_{11}]$, shown by Xie.^[67] These compounds feature the coordination of two arenes towards the silver, but just one anion coordinating. In the remaining structures, usually just one arene is coordinating.^[62, 65–66] The arenes in $[\text{Ag}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6)_2][\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{F}]$ are oriented in the same direction,^[63] while the arenes in $[\text{Ag}(\textit{p}\text{-Me}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{Cl}_{11}]$ are oriented to opposite directions.^[67] In the literature-known structure of $[\text{Ag}(\text{odfb})_2][\text{Al}(\text{OC}(\text{CF}_3)_3)_4]$, the arenes are shifted towards each other and therefore show contacts to the silver with their carbon atoms in the 3-position, as well.^[68]

An attempt to show the bulk purity of the obtained material via powder XRD failed, as the pattern obtained did not match the simulation from the molecular structure (see SI). We assume that the complex loses ligand molecules during the grinding and therefore undergoes structural changes. To corroborate our assumption, we ground a sample of $[\text{Ag}(\text{odfb})_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ and analyzed it by NMR afterwards. The analysis showed the loss of approximately half a molecule of 1,2-difluorobenzene per $[\text{Ag}(\text{odfb})_2]^+$. This would be in accordance to the formation of a $[\text{Ag}_2(\text{odfb})_3][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]_2$ type complex (see Equation 22).

To prove the presence of silver, NMR experiments with $[\text{Ag}(\text{odfb})_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ and substoichiometric amounts of triphenylphosphane were conducted (see SI). There, the ³¹P NMR signal of the PPh₃ ligand was split into two signals, separated by about 563 Hz, which is in the expected region of an ¹J_{P,Ag} coupling constant for complexes of silver with two ligands.^[69] However, due to the notable peak broadening, we were unable to distinguish between the signal sets for the ¹⁰⁷Ag and ¹⁰⁹Ag isotopologues.

Application as Oxidation Agent: As possible application, we used the $[\text{Ag}(\text{odfb})_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ to oxidize ferrocene to ferrocenium ($\text{Fc}/[\text{Fc}]^+$, see Equation 23), as well as tris-4-bromophenylamine to the ‘magic blue’ radical cation (see Equation 24). Both reactions were performed in *o*DFB and featured an immediate color change to intensive blue upon addition of the solvent.

Crystals of $[\text{Fc}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ were grown from a solution in *o*DFB and C₆F₆ at –40 °C. The molecular structure (see Figure 12, left) was solved in the space group *Pbcm* and features two units of $[\text{Fc}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ per unit cell. In the ferrocenium cation, the iron is disordered to two close positions, with one making up 91 % of the occupancy. The cyclopentadienyl rings are nearly eclipsed,

Figure 12. Synthesis of $[\text{Fc}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ and $[\text{N}(4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br})_3][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]\cdot(\textit{oDFB})$ from $[\text{Ag}(\text{odfb})_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ in *o*DFB. Both structures are shown with probabilities of 50%. In the structure of $[\text{Fc}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$, the Fe atom is disordered on two close positions, of which the most populated one (91 %) is shown here. (*Pbcm*, *R*₁: 4.38 %, *wR*₂: 13.75 %, *a* = 7.2745(4) Å, *b* = 15.0966(7) Å, *c* = 17.9248(8) Å, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$). The solvent molecule in the structure of $[\text{N}(4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br})_3][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]\cdot(\textit{oDFB})$ was omitted for clarity. (*P2*₁/*c*, *R*₁: 3.00 %, *wR*₂: 7.98 %, *a* = 9.9719(6) Å, *b* = 22.3926(14) Å, *c* = 15.1216(9) Å, $\alpha = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 103.884(3)^\circ$).

with a twist angle of about 1.5° and almost coplanar, while the Fe–C bond lengths to the most populated Fe site are similar with lengths between 207.1(3) and 209.9(4) pm and an average of 208.5 pm. The Fe site is furthermore surrounded by four anions, with two contacts of 361.68(19) pm and two of 411.0(5) pm between the most populated iron site to the closest fluorine atoms of these anions. In comparison, structures of the $[\text{Fc}]^+$ cation with WCAs are reported for the $[\text{FAl}(\text{OC}(\text{C}_6\text{F}_5)_3)_3]^+$,^[70] $[\text{B}(3,5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CF}_3)_2)_4]^-$ ^[70,71] and the $[\text{B}(\text{C}_6\text{F}_5)_4]^-$ ^[73] anion, in which only the cp-rings of the $[\text{Fc}][\text{B}(\text{C}_6\text{F}_5)_4]$ are almost eclipsed as well. However, in this ferrocenium cation, the Fe–C bond lengths are shorter. Similar to the structure shown in this work, the Fe site is also surrounded by four fluorine atoms, of which two distances are shorter than the others.^[73]

For the $[\text{N}(4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br})_3][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$, a structure could be determined by crystallization from *o*DFB with *n*-pentane (see Figure 12, right). The structure of the $[\text{N}(4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br})_3][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ can be described as alternating layers of cations in the *b,c*-plane on the one hand and anions with *o*DFB molecules on the other. The closest contacts between the nitrogen and the nearest fluorine atom of a neighboring anion are 315.20(15) and 320.85(15) pm and therefore beyond the sum of the van der Waals radii of 310 pm.^[61] The coordination environment of the nitrogen is planar with a sum of C–N–C angles of exactly 360°. The arenes are tilted to each other with angles between 28.15(18) and 43.39(14)° and an average of 36.00°. The literature known $[\text{N}(4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br})_3][\text{Al}(\text{OC}(\text{CF}_3)_3)_4]$ ^[74] is similarly planar, but one

of the arenes is tilted further, while the two remaining have a similar tilt angle.

Conclusions

We showed methods to synthesize large scales of the $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$ anion in an easy and reproducible fashion, as well as an upscaled protocol for the $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ anion and furthermore provided video documentation and tutorials for the syntheses. Especially the $[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]^-$ is now accessible in scales, that would previously be virtually unaffordable by commercial means. Therefore, this work might be of interest for anyone in need of a stable WCA, e.g. in catalysis or battery science. The path to the synthesis of even larger amounts of the undecafluorinated carborate $[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]^-$ is now open, although it still requires the handling of aHF and elemental fluorine gas. Starting from $\text{Na}[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$, we showed the synthesis of some commonly used reagents.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available for download. It contains experimental details, experimental NMR, vibrational and mass spectra, cyclic voltammograms, single crystal and powder X-ray diffraction data, as well as quantumchemical calculation results (203 pages). Deposition Numbers 2354589 (for $(\text{B}(\text{O}i\text{Pr})\text{O})_3$), 2354590 (for $[\text{NHMe}_3][\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$), 2354591 (for $\text{Cs}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$), 2354592 (for $\text{Cs}[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$), 2354593 (for $[\text{Ph}_3\text{C}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$), 2354594 (for $[\text{Ag}(\text{odfb})_2][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$), 2354595 (for $[\text{Fc}][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$) 2354596 (for $[\text{N}(4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br})_3][\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}] \cdot (\text{oDBF})$) contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data are provided free of charge by the joint Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre and Fachinformationszentrum Karlsruhe Access Structures service. All synthetic steps for the syntheses of $[\text{NHMe}_3][\text{B}_{11}\text{H}_{14}]$, $[\text{NHMe}_3][\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$, $\text{Na}[\text{CB}_{11}\text{H}_{12}]$ and $\text{Na}[\text{CHB}_{11}\text{F}_{11}]$ were documented in comprehensive and descriptive video material. The videos are available in the Supporting Information section to download, as well as under <https://www.krossing-group.de/video-tutorials/>.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

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